

MEDICAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF THE HORMONAL PROFILE OF WOMEN WITH POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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Abstract

According to modern data, polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) occurs in 8-10% of women of reproductive age. This is a pathology of the reproductive system, which is manifested by changes in the endocrine organs, the cardiovascular system and causes metabolic disorders. Changes in the ovaries are symptomatically manifested by disorders of the menstrual cycle such as oligo or amenorrhea, the appearance of cysts and, as a result, the development of infertility. Regulation of the release of hormones by the ovaries is regulated by complex neuro-humoral interactions. **The purpose of the study** was: to analyze the medical histories of women who were treated in the gynecological department regarding their hormonal profile and to establish a connection with the development of PCOS. **Materials and methods.** The work uses data from medical histories of women in the gynecological department who were treated in the department and who were diagnosed with PCOS. For analysis, 19 histories of diseases were selected, which were in hospital conditions and were treated for: cysts, ovaries, endometritis, menstrual cycle disorders. Women of reproductive age from 25 to 35 years. In the list of examinations, they were given a study of the hormonal profile of the hormones of the reproductive system. Research results. Our analysis of the disease histories of women who were treated in the gynecological department established hormonal changes in women with PCOS. **The results** of the ultrasound examination, manifestations of hirsutism, laboratory examination data on the level of androgens, and the presence of anovulatory cycles were taken into account. Based on this, 3 research groups A, B and C were formed. Phenotype A in women with hyperandrogenism, ovulation disorders, ultrasound manifestations of polycystic ovaries; phenotype B - hyperandrogenism, ovulation disorders; phenotype C - hyperandrogenism, ultrasound manifestation of polycystic ovarian morphology. **Conclusions.** Our analysis of disease histories between the level of hormones of the reproductive panel of women established a reliable connection between the increase in the level of androgens and LH in the blood plasma and the decrease in estradiol. Shifts in the FSH/LH ratio did not have a significant relationship between PCOS and changes.

Keywords: polycystic ovary syndrome, follicle-stimulating hormone, luteinizing hormone.

Introduction. According to modern data, polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) occurs in 8-10% of women of reproductive age. This is a pathology of the reproductive system, which is manifested by changes in the endocrine organs, the cardiovascular system and causes metabolic disorders. Changes in the ovaries are symptomatically manifested by disorders of the menstrual cycle such as oligo or amenorrhea, the appearance of cysts and, as a result, the development of infertility. Regulation of the release of hormones by the ovaries is regulated by complex neuro-humoral interactions [6]. This process begins with the release of gonadotropic releasing factors by neurons of the hypothalamus, which, based on the principle of negative feedback, cause the production of gonadotropic hormones in a cyclical manner. Follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) is responsible for the growth and maturation of follicles, and luteinizing hormone (LH), which, along with oxytocin, is responsible for ovulation [7]. Under the influence of FSH and LH, appropriate changes occur in the ovaries. A maturing follicle is a source of estrogens, the level of which increases from day 1 to day 14 of the 28th menstrual cycle. According to the principle of feedback, estrogens through the hypothalamic-pituitary link stimulate the production of LH, ovulation and the formation

of the corpus luteum, which is a source of progesterone. Progesterone is responsible for changes on the part of the endometrium of the uterus, namely the processes of proliferation and secretion. The walls of the maturing follicle are a source of both estrogens and androgens. In women with PCOS, excessive production of LH is associated with impaired follicle formation and greater sensitivity of the receptor of theca cells to LH, which is accompanied by hyperandrogenism [8]. The mechanism of PCOS development is heterogeneous and a classification was formed back in 1990, which took into account many subcategories of the manifestation of this disease. A prerequisite is the presence of the Rotterdam criteria associated with hyperandrogenism and anovulatory cycles, which made it possible to identify certain phenotypes of PCOS pathology. Type A includes all three criteria: chronic oligo/amenorrhea, ultrasound signs of PCOS, and laboratory-confirmed hyperandrogenism. Type B combines hyperandrogenism and chronic anovulation, type C - hyperandrogenism and ultrasound signs and D - chronic anovulation and ultrasound signs. In some studies, data were given on the peculiarities of the distribution of different phenotypes depending on the country, race, and there is even a difference in the clinical presentations of patients with

PCOS. The considered biochemical mechanisms of PCOS development indicate insulin resistance in women with PCOS. It is insulin that is responsible for steroidogenesis in the theca cells of the ovaries and, together with insulin-like growth factor and LH, enhances the expression of CYP450c17 mRNA and triggers excessive production of androgens [10].

At the current level, specialists consider the causes of PCOS as multifactorial, which is confirmed by biochemical, molecular studies and genetic examinations.

The purpose of the study was: to analyze the medical histories of women who were treated in the gynecological department regarding their hormonal profile and to establish a connection with the development of PCOS.

Materials and methods. The work uses data from medical histories of women in the gynecological department who were treated in the department and who were diagnosed with PCOS. For analysis, 19 histories of diseases were selected, which were in hospital conditions from 09/2/2023 to 04/23/2024 and were treated for: cysts, ovary, endometritis, menstrual cycle disorders. Women of reproductive age from 25 to 35 years. In the list of examinations, they were given a study of the hormonal profile of the hormones of the reproductive system. And they also determined a test for insulin resistance. In the list of examinations, an ultrasound examination of the pelvic organs was mandatory. These examinations are necessary for the classification of PCOS according to their phenotypic manifestation.

The study of the hormonal profile of women was carried out using the analysis of the disease histories of women who had a clinical diagnosis of PCOS confirmed by clinical and laboratory data. The results of the ultrasound examination were taken into account to

determine the type of PCOS. The following indicators of the hormonal profile were taken into account: FSH - follicle-stimulating hormone; LH - luteinizing hormone; TSH - pituitary thyroid hormone; E2 - estradiol; T - testosterone; free T - free testosterone; A4 - androstenedione; DGEA-C - dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate; DHT - dihydrotestosterone; 17-OPH - 17-hydroxyprogesterone. A control group was compared between phenotypes A and B, between phenotypes A and C, and between phenotypes B and C of polycystic ovary syndrome. Statistical analysis of the obtained data was carried out using a package of application programs ("StatSoft" USA and "Stat Graf"). The data obtained in the experimental and control groups were compared. The following statistical indicators were calculated: arithmetic mean, root mean square deviation, standard error. The parametric Student's t-test was used to assess the differences in mean values with the normal nature of the distribution of sample populations.

Research results. Our analysis of disease histories of women who were treated in the gynecological department established hormonal changes in women with PCOS. The results of the ultrasound examination, manifestations of hirsutism, laboratory examination data on the level of androgens, and the presence of anovulatory cycles [24,33] were taken into account. Based on this, 3 research groups A, B and C were formed. Phenotype A in women with hyperandrogenism, ovulation disorders, ultrasound manifestations of polycystic ovaries; phenotype B - hyperandrogenism, ovulation disorders; phenotype C - hyperandrogenism, ultrasound manifestation of polycystic ovarian morphology. The data of laboratory examinations are listed in the table (see Table 1).

Table 1.

The content of prolactin, estradiol and testosterone in the blood, the ratio of follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) / luteinizing hormone (LH) in women with polycystic ovary syndrome of phenotypes A, B, C

Groups	Hormones								
	Prolactin mme/l	LH mme/l FSH mMe/l	E2 pmol/l	17 - OPG nmol/l	T nmol/l	A4nmol/l	DHT pg/ml	svT pmol/l	DGEA- C pmol/l
CONTROL	333,0 (131,2– 750,0)	0,745 (0,3– 1,6)	324,3 (187,7– 461,6)	1,99 (1,2– 2,6)	1,13 (0,1– 3,7)	4,2 (1,0–7,8)	279 (231– 386)	6,16 (1,7– 6,3)	4,87 (1,79– 10,0)
(19)	287,3* (116,8– 323,9)	1,38*, *** (0,7– 3,0)	204* (99,7– 332,0)	4,08* (2,3– 10,1)	4,1* (1,2– 6,4)	7,4* (1,3– 31,8)	388,7*, ** (185– 858)	7,2 (1,2– 18,7)	7,7* (1,1– 9,8)
Phenotype A (8)	399,5 (124,4– 583,8)	1,07 (0,44– 4,1)	187* (123– 978)	3,8* (2,3– 13,1)	4,0* (0,6– 10,7)	7,6* (1,4– 19,6)	690*, # (158– 2889)	9,9* (1,7– 13,4)	7,5* (1,5– 45,0)
Phenotype B (5)	244,6* (125,4– 572,8)	1,0 (0,3– 2,3)	243,8* (95– 1150)	4,1* (1,5– 12,8)	3,4* (1,2– 7,0)	7,4* (2,8– 21,8)	440,6* (139,9– 2184,7)	9,6* (1,5– 42,2)	8,7* (2,5– 20,2)

Note. FSH - follicle-stimulating hormone; LH - luteinizing hormone; TSH - pituitary thyroid hormone; E2 - estradiol; T - testosterone; free T - free testosterone; A4 - androstenedione; DGEA-C - dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate; DHT - dihydrotestosterone; 17-OPH - 17-hydroxyprogesterone. * Comparison with the control group, $p < 0.05$. ** comparison between phenotypes A and B of polycystic ovary syndrome, $p < 0.05$. *** comparison between phenotypes A and C of polycystic ovary syndrome, $p < 0.05$. # comparison between phenotypes B and C of polycystic ovary syndrome, $p < 0.05$.

When analyzing the data we received, we paid attention to pronounced hormonal changes in the growth of the LH/FSH ratio, an increase in total testosterone and free T was noted, in women of all phenotypes, especially with phenotype A from the class, these indicators were reliably 3.8 times higher than in women without symptoms of PCOS. In patients with phenotype A of PCOS, the level of testosterone significantly exceeded the indicators not only of the control group, but also in women of groups B and C [15,34]. The obtained data correlate with those from literary sources. Hyperandrogenism is one of the main symptoms of PCOS. Phenotypic manifestations of hyperandrogenism are signs of hirsutism, especially when the level of free testosterone is increased. Oligomenorrhoea, anovulation are signs of androgeny, which characterizes the manifestations of PCOS in women from group A. When conducting examinations, I usually determine the total testosterone in blood serum. But the release of testosterone is cyclic and depends on the phases of the menstrual cycle [18,35]. The pulsating nature of the secretion of prehormones by the adrenal glands and cyclic processes in the ovaries during the menstrual cycle cause fluctuations in the concentration of androgens in the blood. Sometimes errors may occur when determining the level of testosterone and phenotypic manifestations of hyperandrogenism, which are one of the main criteria for establishing a diagnosis of PCOS [2,5,7,15,32].

The physiological course of the menstrual cycle depends on the cyclic release of gonadotropic hormones FSH and LH. Changes in their ratio can be a manifestation of PCOS. Thus, in the data we obtained, we observe a significant increase in the level of LH in women with phenotype A by 2.01 times compared to the control group. In groups B and C, the level of LH was slightly higher by 1.2 and 1.15 times, respectively. According to the literature, an elevated level of LH is found in 75% of women with PCOS, which is a consequence of the high amplitude and frequency of its secretion by the pituitary gland. Some researchers point to the unreliability of the LH/FSH ratio criteria for PCOS diagnosis. This is associated with the pulsating nature of LH secretion, which limits the value of its single determination. The ratio of LH/FSH in patients with PCOS phenotype A significantly exceeded the indicators in the control group and in patients with phenotype C [5,8,14,19,28]. The table shows that women with PCOS of all three phenotypes have a decrease in the level of estradiol and a significant increase in the level of 17-OPH, testosterone, A4, DHT and free T in blood serum, compared to the control group. However, no significant differences were found between the estradiol content and the increase in testosterone levels in the blood of women with PCOS with various conditions. In women with phenotype B, the content of DHT exceeded such indicators in groups A and C, and these indicators had a high degree of reliability.

The increase in androgen levels is associated with the aromatase P450 enzyme, which promotes the production of estrogens. Usually it is FSH that regulates the level of aromatase P 450. When the concentration

of androgens increases, aromatase inhibits the production of estrogen. This can cause problems with the menstrual cycle and fertility. According to the literature, a decrease in the level of estradiol, the liver and fat cells produce less TSH, which leads to more free testosterone. In PCOS, fat cells produce less estrogen and more estrone from testosterone, which is normally broken down into estrogen and androstenedione. Some data show that residual estrone in the blood reduces the level of FSH by a negative feedback mechanism and reduces aromatase P450 activity in the cells of the granulosa layer [4,8,9,16,27,35].

Thus, the analysis of the results shows that in women with PCOS there are significant differences in the content of estradiol and free testosterone in the blood serum, but no significant differences in the ratio of LH/FSH between the groups of patients with phenotypes A, B and C were noted, although a significant increase in the level of LH was noted in all phenotypic groups.

Conclusions.

Our analysis of disease histories between the hormone levels of the reproductive panel of women established a reliable relationship between the increase in the level of androgens and LH in the blood plasma and the decrease in estradiol. Shifts in the FSH/LH ratio did not have a significant relationship between PCOS and changes.

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